

NeutrinoReview: CONCEPT PROPOSAL FOR AN OPEN SOURCE REVIEW MANAGEMENT TOOL

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Abstract

This paper proposes the design of NeutrinoReview, a tool that aims to guide scientists through the systematic review process. Based on an extensive literature review and discussions with experienced scientists from WHO, a conceptual design is suggested that combines state-of-the-art solutions and further reduces human effort by seamlessly integrating them into a single solution. This concept serves as an initial step towards a comprehensive solution that automates the whole systematic review process with a continuous user interface, thereby significantly improving user experience. This paper aims to present the idea of NeutrinoReview to the broader research community at a very early stage, with the aim of further refining and expanding this promising concept in an open and collaborative manner.

INTRODUCTION

In 1753, the medical researcher James Lind conducted the first systematic literature review [1]. Since then, systematic reviews (SRs) have become a common practice in supporting evidence-based medicine and are widely used as a research methodology in various fields beyond healthcare. For example, Kitchenham constructed specific guidelines for performing SR in software engineering research. He describes a systematic literature review as a method for identifying, evaluating, and synthesizing all research relevant to a specific research question, topic area, or phenomenon of interest [2].

Since SRs aim to identify all relevant research, this research methodology demands significant human effort. Conducting a SR requires a substantial amount of time, typically ranging from 6 months to 2 years [3, 4].

To minimize this workload, several research efforts aimed to apply information technology, especially artificial intelligence (AI) and natural language processing (NLP) to support experts in the SR process. While certain steps have been effectively automated, others require additional research and advancement [5].

To facilitate collaboration and enable different automation tools to work together more effectively, the International Collaboration for the Automation of Systematic Reviews (ICASR) was formed. In their initial meeting, they formulated the ‘Vienna Principles’ to propose that solutions should be offered as specialized modules designed for specific tasks, compatible with standardized file types, enabling researchers

to assemble a sequence of tools that best fit their specific needs [6].

This approach offers adaptability but requires exporting results from each stage and then re-importing them into subsequent tools, which represents a redundant extra effort. Additionally, it requires that experts familiarize themselves with a variety of tools and their distinct user interfaces.

To address these challenges, this paper suggests a conceptual design of a comprehensive SR automation tool that eliminates the need for additional tools to conduct SRs. This novel tool, named NeutrinoReview, will offer intuitive and continuous user interaction throughout the entire process, starting from the development of the project protocol and continuing through to data extraction. Its objective is to automate a maximum number of tasks and enhance human efficiency in areas where complete automation is not feasible. By integrating the most advanced automation approaches for each step and eliminating transitions between them, this method aims to contribute to faster evidence-based research.

One use case may be the ARIA project, a joint venture between CERN and WHO. The objective of this project is to develop an online tool¹ to quantify the risk of SARS-CoV-2 airborne transmission to inform nonpharmaceutical risk reduction measures in residential, public and health care settings. The underlying model, as estimated internally, is based on more than 100 different parameters which should be supported with evidence based research. Here, the suggested tool could help to execute the required SRs in a feasible timeframe.

However, NeutrinoReview will not be developed to be limited to internal use but rather should become an open-source web application, freely accessible to researchers worldwide and designed for use in SRs across various fields. Furthermore, the motivation for developing the proposed tool includes the fact that with minor adjustments, it can be used for free and unbiased science searches. By removing the restriction to academic papers, a fully automated SR process could greatly contribute to an unbiased, free, and open web search pertinent to an audience beyond academia.

The remainder of the paper continues by describing existing automation approaches for several steps of the SR process, followed by an outline of the applied methodology. Subsequently, the design decisions and conceptual architecture for NeutrinoReview are described. Then, the existing limitations and paths for future work are explained. The pa-

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¹ <https://partnersplatform.who.int/tools/aria>

per concludes by encouraging interested parties to contribute to this endeavor.

BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

Van Dinter et al. systematically reviewed existing literature about the automation of SRs [5]. They identified 41 primary studies focusing on the automation of one or more steps of the SR. Most of the identified studies targeted the (semi-)automation of the screening process, and no solution aimed to cover more than three steps simultaneously. Thus, combining tools designed for specific steps is a common practice. This approach can allow a team of experienced researchers to reduce the duration of a full SR from several months to less than two weeks [7].

Based on the insights stated above, the remainder of this section outlines the SR process and aims to highlight how automation tools can support the human expert at each step.

Project Initiation and Data Retrieval

This phase starts after the research question is defined and an SR is determined as the preferred research methodology. First, a project protocol is developed which offers a detailed description of the research objective, hypothesis, search terms, and criteria to include and exclude studies. The protocol is designed to guarantee reproducibility, making sure that following its prescribed guidelines leads to consistent results, irrespective of the researcher. Templates can help reduce human effort in creating project protocols. This approach was also adopted by Clark et al. to streamline this stage of the process [7].

Search terms, typically determined through collaboration with a librarian or information manager, are then used to formulate a search strategy that prioritizes broad sensitivity and comprehensive data retrieval, rather than being overly specific and risking omission of relevant documents. Subsequently, the formulated strategy is employed to conduct searches across multiple databases. To reduce the time effort at this stage, two tools from the Systematic Review Accelerator (SRA)², a software suite developed at Bond University, were utilized [7]:

- A word frequency analyzer, assisted in developing the search string.
- A tool called 'polgot search translator' was instrumental in adapting the search syntax for compatibility with various databases.

Although their approach involved manually querying multiple databases, amalgamating searches from various source databases could further streamline the process. Metta [8] and EBM Search [9] serve as examples of meta search engines that facilitate SRs.

Prior to further processing, the retrieved studies must be deduplicated, a task that can be accomplished using one of the various available software solutions. The tool Deduplicate,

for instance, excels in this task with an average recall of 99.51% and a precision of 100% [10].

Screening

To determine studies that comply with the specified inclusion and exclusion criteria, each retrieved study is subjected to a thorough screening process. Initially, the researcher assesses only the title and abstract of each paper to eliminate the bulk of the nonrelevant papers and then proceeds to a detailed examination of the full text for comprehensive evaluation. To streamline the screening process Clark et al. utilised RobotSearch [11] during the title and abstract screening phase to filter out documents that are definitely not randomized controlled trials (RCTs), the specific study type to which this SR was limited [7]. However, it is important to consider that the exclusive focus on RCTs notably simplified the screening process. In addition to prefiltration, review management tools are widely utilized for the screening phase of SRs. Their key feature is a user-friendly interface enabling experts to include or exclude studies quickly using hotkeys.

As analysed in a previous publication, most existing tools integrated supervised machine learning approaches like classification and priority ranking to reduce the workload in the screening process [12].

Due to their ability to classify text without requiring fine-tuning or labeled data, general-purpose Large Language Models (LLMs) represent a promising technology for automating literature screening in systematic reviews. Reference [13] evaluated OpenAI's GPT-3.5 Turbo for title and abstract screening, finding that assigning the model roles such as an "experienced researcher" improved performance. Although the model's sensitivity increased with certain prompts, none reached Cochrane's required sensitivity (0.99) [14]. The model performed comparably to less experienced human screeners, despite an expert missing 19% of relevant papers. Similarly, [15] assessed GPT-3.5 on six datasets, finding a weighted average accuracy of 0.907 and a sensitivity for included papers of 0.764. Considering the rapid developments in this field, further performance improvements also in the use case of screening automation can be expected.

While many review management tools provide features for uploading full-text PDF documents, tools like LiteRev [16] automatically retrieves full texts, either from the metadata directly or via a link in the metadata. In the latter case, the text is automatically extracted from the PDF file. Additionally, most reference management software, such as EndNote³, offers semi-automated features for full-text retrieval.

Data Extraction

In [7] the sole technical tool utilized for data extraction was a digital spreadsheet, which functioned as a structured form to systematically capture the necessary data. ExaCT [17] is a tool that uses an information extraction engine to

² <https://sr-accelerator.com>

³ <https://endnote.com>

extract fragments that best describe the characteristics of the trial to support the expert in the data extraction phase.

Ultimately, these gathered insights are documented, culminating in the SR being prepared for submission and publication.

Comprehensive Solutions

To conclude this section, automation tools are available for various stages of the SR process. However, to the best of our knowledge, no existing tool comprehensively facilitates the integration of automation technologies across the entire SR process. Therefore, this paper proposes the development of a tool that combines the most advanced automation approaches and leverages the opportunity to further streamline the process by integrating them into a single, comprehensive tool.

METHODOLOGY

Extensive literature research and discussions with experienced scientists from CERN and WHO, as well as observing their working methods, allowed a detailed analysis of the currently very labor intensive process, highlighted the pain points, and motivated the development of a more advanced software tool that guides scientists through the whole process of a SR. By combining best-practice solutions for individual tasks, as discussed in the previous section, a conceptual architecture was developed for a tool that further streamlines the process and enhances user experience by providing an all-in-one solution. The emphasis was placed on offering a generic solution that is both domain-independent and modular. In addition, tasks that require further research for automation have been identified.

CONCEPTUAL DESIGN

Based on existing automation solutions targeted at certain tasks, this section describes the concept of a software tool that addresses the whole process, starting from the project protocol development and continuing through to data extraction. Only the initial review of the literature and the presentation of the results in a scientific paper are not included in the concept. This is due to two reasons. First, for the ARIA project, no initial literature research is required to identify a suitable research question for an SR. The topic is predetermined by the necessary parameters used in the model. Second, within the ARIA project, the goal is to retrieve evidence-supported numerical values for those parameters. The publication of the results will be considered, but it is not a priority. Furthermore, addressing these steps for a wide audience may be challenging due to domain-specific requirements.

Figure 1 illustrates the conceptual designs suggested for a novel review management tool. It consists of five components that will be detailed subsequently.

Project protocol Development

After creating a new SR instance, the user is presented with a user interface that guides them through the creation of the project protocol. Based on the field in which the SR is created, the input form adapts to the respective domain. For instance, in health-related fields, it may be based on the registration form of the International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO) [18] to ensure that all information is collected at the point of potential registration.

Furthermore, the concept includes a feature that assists the user in creating the search string, which is one of the most critical elements of the protocol regardless of the applied field. This feature could be based on a word frequency analyzer similar to the SRA tool or on generative AI technology.

Data Retrieval

To reduce the chance of omitting relevant studies, various academic libraries are queried in SRs. The choice of libraries is determined by the responsible researcher and varies across different SRs. For example, PubMed⁴, Medline⁵, Embase⁶, and Cochrane⁷ are the most relevant academic libraries for conducting the SRs planned for the ARIA project. Therefore, while these libraries will be prioritized, NeutrinoReview will not be limited to them.

Provided that the academic libraries of interest offer the option to query the database through an Application Programming Interface (API), NeutrinoReview will amalgamate the search across various sources. Since the search string is already known to the tool, this can streamline the database search task to a single click. Additionally, the integrated deduplication software immediately begins preparing the retrieved citations for the screening phase.

Title and Abstract Screening

As previously described in [12], a wide range of tools to support the title and abstract (TiAb) screening phase is available. However, it was also emphasized that the reliability of existing tools is not always transparent and further automation could lead to additional time savings, as this is the most critical task of the SR process.

Given the rapid evolution of foundational LLMs and their demonstrated performance in automating title and abstract screening, this technology emerges as the most promising approach for streamlining the screening phase. An additional advantage is that these models facilitate automation without being restricted to specific research questions or eligibility criteria.

Therefore, NeutrinoReview will reduce the human workload in the TiAb screening phase by integrating LLM-based prefiltration, leaving only those records for human review

⁴ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>

⁵ <https://www.medline.com>

⁶ <https://embase.com>

⁷ <https://www.cochranelibrary.com>

Figure 1: Conceptual architecture of a review management system encompassing the entire systematic review process.

where the underlying model cannot make a definitive exclusion decision. This approach minimizes the risk of excluding relevant papers while still significantly reducing the human workload.

The development of this screening automation necessitates extensive prompt engineering and the comparison of multiple models to identify the most effective one. Additionally, before integrating LLM-based automation, thorough evaluation on human-annotated data is essential to ensure its reliability in replacing human screening.

Finally, the remaining citations have to be manually screened. In this step, the user will be supported with semi-automation features, already approved in existing solutions as summarized in a previous publication [12].

Full-Text Screening

Following the TiAb screening phase, NeutrinoReview will retrieve the full text of included citations, provided that they are open access and available online. Full-text versions purchased by the user can be uploaded for further processing in NeutrinoReview.

By utilizing various information retrieval and NLP methods, including foundational LLMs, relevant passages from the documents will be extracted, and recommendations for inclusion or exclusion decisions will be provided based on the defined criteria. However, in the full-text screening phase, which typically involves a smaller number of citations, the final decision will always be made by the human expert to ensure that no relevant citation is missed at this final stage.

After completing the screening phase, NeutrinoReview will display the results through various visualizations, including diagrams showing the distribution of different exclusion reasons and flow diagrams reporting the applied filtration process.

Data Extraction

In addition to facilitating the data filtration process, NeutrinoReview will be able to assist scientists in extracting data from relevant studies. The software helps create custom templates for data extraction tailored to the specific SR.

In addition, it will automatically extract pertinent information from the full text in the form of value, unit, and context, and will offer suggestions for completing the form. To maintain the quality standards of a SR, these suggestions require validation and approval from a human expert.

As a novel tool, NeutrinoReview guides users through the entire SR process and facilitates the extraction of relevant data at all stages. This includes generating the protocol in both .docx and .pdf formats, maintaining lists of citations in RIS and .csv formats at all stages, and providing the results of the data extraction in at least .csv format.

Comprehensive Solution

Offering the described (semi-)automation systems within a single tool allows for a smooth transition between individual steps. It completely eliminates the need to export results from one tool and import them into another, which not only saves time but also reduces the potential for human error. Furthermore, providing one comprehensive tool is expected to improve the user experience, as all steps are integrated within a consistent UI. Additionally, this approach is anticipated to decrease the training effort required to efficiently utilize the integrated automation technologies.

LIMITATIONS

The presented concept, while promising, confronts several limitations that could affect its feasibility and further development. The reliance on libraries that provide APIs and accessible full-text articles may limit its seamless application, potentially leading to increased human effort. To ensure the quality of SRs, human oversight remains necessary for interpreting complex data and making final decisions. Moreover, ethical considerations and potential biases introduced by AI-based automation require continuous monitoring and adjustment to ensure fair and unbiased reviews. Addressing these issues is crucial for the development of a robust and user-friendly review management system.

FUTURE WORK

Regardless of the presented concept, continuous improvement in the automation of all steps of the SR process remains necessary. Tsafnat et al. outlined potential directions for each step [17]. To achieve complete automation of the process, enhancing the automation of full-text screening and data extraction is particularly important, with recent advancements in large language models (LLMs) offering promising approaches.

To realize the concept presented, organizing the implementation as an open-source project could be instrumental. This approach would encourage contributions from institutions interested in utilizing such a tool and establish partnerships with academic institutions and providers of academic libraries, potentially accelerating development and addressing existing limitations.

Furthermore, once a prototype is developed, its real-world applicability must be evaluated across various research domains. This evaluation should include user experience studies and assessments of time savings and effects on the quality of SRs, providing valuable insights for further refinement of the tool.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this paper suggests the architecture of a novel tool called NeutrinoReview, an open-source software designed to streamline the entire SR process within a single tool. By utilizing state-of-the-art automation technologies and integrating them seamlessly, the proposed concept aims to significantly reduce the substantial human effort currently required to conduct SRs. The CAiMIRA team at CERN, in collaboration with their partners at the WHO, will continue their research and development efforts, with the goal of presenting a first prototype in the near future. This paper invites experts from various fields to challenge the proposed design, suggest improvements, or contribute in any capacity to the implementation and evaluation of this open-source project.

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